

United States Department of the Interior

FISH AND WILDLIFE SERVICE
San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish & Wildlife Office
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Sacramento, California 95814-4700

In reply refer to:
2022-0005810-S7-001

April 7, 2023

Sarah Firestone
Senior Project Manager
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U.S. Army Corps of Engineers
San Francisco District
450 Golden Gate Avenue
San Francisco, California 94102-3406

Subject: Formal Section 7 Consultation on the Halo Ranch Mitigation Bank Project, Sonoma County, California (U.S. Army Corps of Engineers File Number: SPN-2017-00478N)

Dear Ms. Firestone:

This letter is in response to the U.S. Army Corps of Engineers' (Corps') March 15, 2021, letter and subsequent November 28, 2022, emails requesting initiation of formal consultation with the U.S. Fish and Wildlife Service (Service) for the Halo Ranch Mitigation Bank Project (proposed project), near the City of Petaluma, Sonoma County, California. At issue are the proposed project's effects to the federally endangered salt marsh harvest mouse (*Reithrodontomys raviventris*), endangered California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*)¹ and the threatened California red-legged frog (frog) (*Rana draytonii*). This response is provided under the authority of the Endangered Species Act of 1973, as amended (16 U.S.C. 1531 *et seq.*) (Act), and in accordance with the implementing regulations pertaining to interagency cooperation (50 CFR § 402).

The Federal action on which we are consulting is the Corps' issuance of a permit to Mr. Dave Brazil (Applicant) under Section 404 of the Clean Water Act of 1972, as amended, 33 U.S.C. § 1344 *et seq.*, and Section 10 of the Rivers and Harbors Act of 1899, as amended, 33 U.S.C. § 403 *et seq.*, to reestablish/enhance seasonal wetlands, tidal wetlands, and riparian habitat for the purpose of establishing a wetland mitigation bank. The Halo Ranch Mitigation Bank is not seeking federally listed species credits.

¹ Until the Service officially adopts recent nomenclature changes made by the American Ornithologists' Union to Ridgway's Rail (*Rallus obsoletus*), we maintain the use of California clapper rail (*Rallus longirostris obsoletus*) in this correspondence. Note, the change in taxonomic assignment does not change the listing status of the species.

In considering your request, we have based our evaluation on the following: (1) the Corps' November 28, 2022, emails with the attached November 2022 biological assessment by Resource Environmental Solutions (RES); (2) the February 16 and 28, 2023 biological assessment addendums; (3) the draft Halo Ranch Mitigation Bank Banking Enabling Instrument (BEI) dated November 2022; (4) numerous emails and meetings; and (5) other information available to the Service.

Consultation History

July 15, 2020	RES met with the Service to introduce the team members, provide a proposed project overview, and discuss the federally listed species potentially occurring in the Action Area.
March 15, 2021	The Service received the Corps consultation initiation request letter with the January 2021 biological assessment transmitted via the Corps' filesharing platform.
April 23, 2021	The Corps submitted and the Service received the revised biological assessment dated April 2021.
September 14, 2021	The Service, Corps, and RES met to discuss the total duration of project implementation, the amount of available habitat, and species effects determinations.
October 11, 2021	The Service emailed comments on the revised biological assessment.
October 11, 2021	The Corps forwarded an email from RES regarding forthcoming proposed project design changes.
December 8, 2021	RES emailed the Service, responding to the biological assessment comments received on October 11, 2021.
January 20, 2022	RES emailed a memorandum to the Service with updates to the proposed project impacts related to a redesign of the southeastern berm and additional responses to comments received October 11, 2021.
March 11, 2022	The Service emailed the Corps and RES with requests for clarification and additional information.
April 13, 2022	RES emailed a memorandum to the Service with responses to the March 11, 2022 comments.
April 22, 2022	The Service emailed the Corps and RES with requests for clarification.

April 26, 2022 The Service, Corps, and RES met to discuss the outstanding questions from the April 22, 2022 email.

April 27, 2022 The Service emailed the Corps and RES a guide to use for the construction noise impact assessment on California clapper rails.

May 17, 2022 The Service attended an Interagency Review Team meeting for the proposed Halo Ranch Mitigation Bank.

May 27, 2022 RES emailed notes from the May 17, 2022 Interagency Review Team meeting.

May 31, 2022 The Service and other agencies provided comments and requested clarification of the meeting notes. RES emailed revised meeting notes.

June 6, 2022 The Corps emailed agency comments on RES' May 17, 2022, Interagency Review Team presentation.

July 19-20 2022 The Corps and Service exchanged emails regarding proposed project changes and confirmation of changes requiring a revised biological assessment.

September 23, 2022 The Corps sent an email to the Service withdrawing the consultation request due to significant project description changes. The Service responded with confirmation and a staffing change for the consultation when it resumes. RES responded with questions whether to include both bank phases.

September 26, 2022 The Corps and Service responded regarding consulting on one or both phases of the bank and the type of wetlands created.

October 3-13, 2022 The Service and RES exchanged emails regarding bank phases and biological assessment revisions.

November 28, 2022 The Corps emailed the Service the revised biological assessment and effects determinations restarting consultation.

December 20, 2022 The Service requested the Corps resend the draft BEI as the biological assessment referred to information in the BEI.

December 21, 2022 The Service received the draft BEI.

December 28, 2022 The Service and RES exchanged emails regarding the Action Area and construction activities.

February 22, 2023 The Service received an addendum to the biological assessment.

February 24, 2023 The Service and RES exchanged emails.

February 28, 2023 The Service received another addendum to the biological assessment.

BIOLOGICAL OPINION

Description of the Proposed Action

The proposed project involves rehabilitation, re-establishment, and enhancement of tidal wetlands, seasonal wetlands, and riparian and intermittent streams (herein referred to as non-perennial stream or Wheat Creek) on the Halo Ranch Property and maintenance as part of the implementation of the Halo Ranch Mitigation Bank. The Halo Ranch Property is located directly adjacent to the southeastern most boundary of the City of Petaluma, in unincorporated Sonoma County approximately 3.8 miles east-southeast of downtown Petaluma.

The following are the restoration actions that will be conducted as a part of the proposed project:

- Rehabilitate seasonal wetlands within an ephemeral ditch along Lakeville Highway to provide hydrologic connectivity.
- Re-establish seasonal wetlands, including seasonal wetland depressions to mimic historic conditions.
- Rehabilitate a non-perennial stream (Wheat Creek) to promote overbank hydrology to the seasonal wetlands. Raise the elevation of the channel bed to reduce the degree of incision and to encourage flows to fan out onto the seasonal wetlands. Encouraging overbank flows will raise groundwater elevations below the fan surface to enhance the seasonal wetlands conditions. Increase the roughness of the Wheat Creek channel to promote dissipation of energy and promote overbank flows to restore non-linear flow paths.
 - Construct a berm on the southeastern side of the property that runs parallel to Wheat Creek, outside of the riparian corridor, that connects from Overflow Point 1 to Overflow Point 3. The berm will ensure hydrological flows will be retained within the Project Area.
- Establish non-wetland riparian habitat along both banks of the Wheat Creek corridor.
- Re-establish tidal wetlands and rehabilitate tidal wetlands by removing tidal gates and lowering the berm along the southern and western boundaries of the Project Area. Excavate tidal channels within the Project Area to maximize tidal hydrology connectivity and function. Remove soil stockpiles and raise subsided areas within the tidal wetlands areas to create and sustain a functioning tidal wetland ecosystem.
- Enhance tidal wetlands along the western tidally-influenced ditch by improving hydrologic connections to tidal waters.

Earthmoving Activities

Excavated material will be redistributed within the Project Area. A portion of this material will be redistributed within the southern portion of the Project Area (outside of the newly constructed

tidal channels) to raise elevations and to raise the elevation of the channel bed of Wheat Creek. A total of approximately 32,915 cubic yards of cut and fill material will be used in order to complete the proposed project.

Ephemeral Ditches, Basin, and Swale

The ephemeral ditch (ED-1) that runs parallel to Lakeville Highway at the Project Area's northwestern extent will be rehabilitated as seasonal wetlands to increase flows onto the re-established seasonal wetlands. An earthen plug will be installed within a short segment of ephemeral ditch (ED-1) near Culvert 1 and the creek bed will be raised on both sides of the earthen plug to create a shallow swale feature. The seasonal wetland swale created between the earthen plug and Culvert 2 will convey flows towards Culvert 2 and into a basin before the seasonal wetland swale outlets onto the restored seasonal wetlands.

Overbank flows will be rehabilitated along the northwestern ephemeral ditch (ED-2) by removing spoil piles, woody debris, and lowering the banks to allow shallow flows to disperse onto the adjacent restored seasonal wetlands. Overflow Point 5 is designed to encourage these flows onto the restored seasonal wetlands at this specific location during large storm events.

The ephemeral ditch (ED-3) that runs parallel to an ephemeral ditch (ED-2) will be graded to the same elevation as the restored seasonal wetlands. This feature (ED-3) does not currently maintain a connection up or downstream to either ephemeral ditch (ED-2) or the tidally-influenced ditch (TD-1).

Non-perennial Stream (Wheat Creek)

Non-perennial stream rehabilitation will be completed along the entire length of the Wheat Creek corridor. Approximately 310 cubic yards material will be excavated and 3,150 of fill material will be added to the bed of Wheat Creek to raise the bed to the elevation of the adjacent seasonal wet meadow from below Culvert 4 at Lakeville Highway to Overflow Point 3. This will encourage overbank flows to the surrounding restored seasonal wetlands. Three overflow points will be created to encourage flows to spread out onto the restored seasonal wetlands. Overflow Point 1 is located closest to Lakeville Highway, Overflow Point 2 is located midway downstream, and Overflow Point 3 is located at the southern portion of Wheat Creek where it currently transitions into tidally-influenced stream. Further descriptions of the overflow points are outlined below:

- Overflow Point 1: Overflow Point 1 will include vegetated rock armor in order to reduce velocities and sheer stresses which will be at their highest during large storm events as flows enter the Halo Ranch Property. Biodegradable erosion control fabric will be used to protect bare soil and temporary irrigation may be used to establish vegetative cover.
- Overflow Point 2: Flows will be encouraged to flow onto the restored seasonal wetlands through swale-like features on either bank, similar to Overflow Points 1 and 3.
- Overflow Point 3: At the downstream end of rehabilitated Wheat Creek, Overflow Point 3 will be created by placing earthen material up to two feet above the adjacent restored seasonal wetlands elevation to end the flows and allow discharge to spread out onto the

restored seasonal wetlands instead of maintaining the current connection downstream to the Petaluma River. Downstream of Overflow Point 3, the creek bed will continue to be raised in elevation and will eventually align with the elevation of the restored tidal wetlands channels extending from the historic Petaluma River main channel.

Additionally, a wooden bridge that crosses Wheat Creek will be removed. Removal of the bridge will restore this portion of Wheat Creek.

Non-wetland Riparian

Non-wetland riparian establishment will be completed along the entire length of the rehabilitated Wheat Creek corridor. During the rehabilitation of Wheat Creek, the banks of the creek will be graded as described above. No additional earthmoving activities are included for establishment of non-wetland riparian habitat. It is anticipated that the overflow points along Wheat Creek will encourage flows through the non-wetland riparian corridor and out onto the restored seasonal wetlands.

A berm will be constructed approximately 75 feet from the eastern bank of Wheat Creek (outside of the non-wetland riparian habitat) to maintain hydrologic flows within the Project Area. The berm will be approximately eight feet in height with 3:1 side slope and will include approximately 3,125 cubic yards of fill material. The northern extent of the berm will begin adjacent to Overflow Point 1 and the southern extent of the berm will be adjacent to Overflow Point 3. The berm will be parallel to Wheat Creek for the entire extent until it makes a connection to Overflow Point 3. This will ensure that hydrologic flows are maintained within the seasonal wetlands instead of flowing south into the tidal wetlands.

Seasonal Wetlands

The area being restored as seasonal wetlands will include restoration of seasonal wet meadow and seasonal wetland depressions. The majority of the restored seasonal wet meadow will not include grading; however, the seasonal wetland depressions will be graded to a minimum depth of 6 inches and an estimated 3:1 slope. Seasonal wetland depressions will vary in depth and slope to account for hydrology across the landscape. To the extent feasible, grading will follow natural contours and existing depressional areas. Approximately 11,150 cubic yards of material will be excavated in order to create the seasonal wetland depressions.

Seasonal wetland depression re-establishment will occur along the portion of the Halo Ranch Property closest to Lakeville Highway. The depressions will collect local rainfall and runoff in areas that will not receive overland flow directly from Wheat Creek or from the rehabilitated seasonal wetland swales. The depressions will be placed in both uplands and within the seasonal wet meadow to create a seasonal wet meadow/depression complex.

In addition, re-establishment of seasonal wet meadow will occur within the eastern portion of the Halo Ranch Property, on either side of Wheat Creek. Material will be cut and filled within this area to excavate the seasonal wetland depressions. This will create a smooth transition between the tidal wetlands to the south with a gradual increase in gradient to the seasonal wet meadow to

the north.

Tidal Wetlands

Tidal hydrology will be restored to the Halo Ranch Property by lowering the existing agricultural berms along the southern and western boundaries of the Halo Ranch Property to six feet above mean sea level, and removal of Flap Gate 1 and Flap Gate 2. The elevations within the restored tidal wetlands will include mud flats, low marsh, and high marsh, as the tidal wetlands connect to the lower elevations of the restored seasonal wetlands. Approximately 15,190 cubic yards of material will be excavated and approximately 26,380 cubic yards of fill material will be used to create the tidal wetlands and tidal wetland channels. A total of approximately 32,195 cubic yards of cut and fill material will be used in order to complete the restoration of tidal wetlands.

- **Enhancement:** Enhancement of tidal wetlands will occur along the western boundary of the Project Area within the tidally-influenced ditch (TD-1). Flap Gate 1 will be removed which will allow tidal fluctuations and natural recruitment by tidal wetland vegetation onto the Project Area. Material will be removed to create the appropriate elevation of tidal wetlands marsh habitat.
- **Rehabilitation:** Rehabilitation of tidal wetlands will occur within the southern portion of the Project Area. The existing agricultural berm along the southern boundary of the Project Area will be lowered to approximately six feet above mean sea level creating a high marsh zone. The lowering of the berm will create excess material. This material will be sidecast on the interior side of the berm to create a gradual transition in elevation between the adjacent Petaluma River/marsh complex and the Halo Ranch Property.

Tidal channels will be excavated within the Project Area and connected to existing channels in the tidal marsh complex by excavating through the agricultural berm at three locations as described below. Material will be excavated and sidecast raising adjacent lowlands and some low-point brackish marsh areas to an elevation of five feet above mean sea level. This raise in elevation will promote the growth of tidal marsh vegetation.

Two tidal connections will be made at the southern extent of the existing Wheat Creek corridor, one on the east bank and one directly opposite it on the west bank. These two connections, along with the connection at Flap Gate 2, will allow tidal flushing of the created channels and rehabilitated tidal marsh within the Halo Ranch Property.

The outlet of the existing Wheat Creek corridor will be excavated in order to connect the existing tidal channel network within the Petaluma River/marsh complex with the rehabilitated tidal channel network within the Halo Ranch Property. Material excavated will be sidecast into the Halo Ranch Property as discussed above.

- **Re-establishment:** Tidal wetlands will be re-established along the boundary between the tidal wetlands and restored seasonal wetlands. Material will be removed from high points and redistributed in place to create a more gradual transition in elevation from restored tidal wetlands to seasonal wetlands.

Additionally, tidal wetlands will be re-established within the Halo Ranch Project along the top and inward side of the berm that will be lowered as a part of construction. The lowering of the berm will create excess material. This material will be sidecast on the interior side of the berm to create a gradual transition in elevation between the adjacent Petaluma River/marsh complex and the Halo Ranch Property.

Transitional Uplands and Trees

During construction, ground disturbance is anticipated to occur primarily along access haul routes and upland areas adjacent to Lakeville Highway. Any ground disturbance to upland areas within the Halo Ranch Property will be revegetated.

Planting Plan

The Halo Ranch Property will be seeded and planted with direct transplant material (plugs) to promote and accelerate vegetation establishment within the restored seasonal wetlands, non-perennial stream (Wheat Creek) and non-wetland riparian habitats. The methods of planting and seeding are further defined in the grading and planting plans and incorporate lessons learned from other similar restoration efforts.

Seeding will commence after grading and all earthwork are completed. Seeding, direct transplant material, and willow stake installation will ideally occur just prior to the onset of the rainy season post-construction.

Seed

To the extent feasible, seed will be sourced from the local region, with preference to the Sonoma County area, to improve local adaptations that will increase success rates for germination and plant establishment. The specific seeds used depend on availability. However, species lists are included in the biological assessment for the preferred species for the restored habitats.

Seed will be broadcast with tractor operated mechanical broadcast seeders. The mechanical broadcast seeder will need to be calibrated to plant seed at the proper rates. Following the broadcast seeding, seed will be harrowed and/or-ring-rolled, to ensure proper seed to soil contact.

Direct Transplant Materials

As part of routine maintenance of the agricultural stock pond, the Property Owner will remove soils that have collected over time thereby reducing the holding capacity of the agricultural stock pond north of the Halo Ranch Property. Plant clusters will be removed from these soils and transplanted into the restored seasonal wetlands in the Halo Ranch Property south of Lakeville Highway in “groups”. Species chosen for transplant are those identified as naturally occurring within the area; therefore, it is anticipated they are more likely to establish successfully. Timing of agricultural stock pond maintenance will occur prior to the onset of the rainy season.

A cluster and groups of clusters method will be used for the proposed project to increase the success of the plant installation effort. The direct transplant material will be cut into clusters and planted in groups with the guidance of a biologist who will help guide the best placement of plantings during installation. Cluster groups will primarily be focused in low lying areas, including the seasonal wetland depressions and lower elevation areas of the seasonal wet meadow.

Willow Stakes

Willow stakes will be salvaged from within the Property Owner's land. Several well-established willow trees will provide ample stake material without causing stress to these existing trees. No more than 50% of each donor live willow will be harvested.

Willow stakes are best obtained during winter while plants are dormant (generally December through March, species dependent). As feasible, stakes will be installed the same day they are harvested; otherwise, they will be kept moist until installation. Willow stakes will preferably be installed by pushing into the soil by hand.

Restored Habitats

Ephemeral ditch (ED-1) that runs parallel to Lakeville Highway will be revegetated post-construction to reduce erosion during the first rainy season and will ultimately be part of the restored seasonal wetlands, supplementing the hydrology of this system. The ephemeral ditch that runs along the northwestern corner of the Project Area (ED-3) will also be revegetated post-construction. The basin and swale constructed as part of the ephemeral ditch along Lakeville Highway will also be reseeded and planted post-construction. The ephemeral ditch (ED-2) that runs parallel to the Ellis Creek Water Recycling Facility will be revegetated to reduce erosion and enhance the quality of the habitat post-construction.

The banks of the rehabilitated Wheat Creek channel will be seeded with the same seed mix as for established non-wetland riparian. Seeding will help provide a more uniform planting effort when combined with the non-wetland riparian plantings to occur on either bank of the creek. Overflow Point 1 will include placement of vegetated rock armor and will be planted intermittently between the rocks with willow stakes. Additionally, woody debris such as partially embedded live willow logs will be placed at Overflow Point 1 to reduce erosive forces as flows first enter the Project Area at the northern extent of Wheat Creek within the Project Area.

Established non-wetland riparian habitat will be revegetated with a seed mix of native wetland and riparian grasses and forbs to mimic natural non-perennial stream systems found in the region. Willow stakes will be installed along the entire established non-wetland riparian corridor at 10-foot on center spacing. Approximately 1,980 willow stakes will be installed, including 990 red willow and 990 arroyo willow. Red willow and Arroyo willow will be installed with an even number of each species along both banks.

Seasonal wet meadow and seasonal wetland depressions will be seeded and planted with plant species as identified in the biological assessment. Seasonal wet meadow and seasonal wetland

depressions will use the same plant palette; however, quantities of each species may vary slightly between the two areas. Seeding and planting will be conducted after earthmoving activities are completed. Areas outside of the limits of disturbance will retain existing vegetation (mowed to stubble height) to help reinforce soils while the native plant community becomes established. As a result of grading of the restored tidal wetlands, the groundwater table is anticipated to rise, increasing hydrology to the restored seasonal wetlands to support vegetative growth. Approximately 480,000 individual plants will be installed within the restored seasonal wetlands.

Tidal wetlands are expected to revegetate through natural recruitment over time and will not be planted.

Transitional upland areas, currently either agricultural fields or ruderal/disturbed habitat, will be restored to native annual grassland. Transitional uplands will be seeded with a native upland species erosion control mix to protect from erosion during the first rainy season post-construction and to reduce the establishment of non-native invasive species.

Irrigation

The source of water for the restored habitats will be direct precipitation and rainwater runoff; the Project Area is not anticipated to require artificial irrigation to ensure success of plant/seed installation. However, temporary irrigation may be used during the first one to three years following installation of willow stakes to help with establishment and increase survivorship rates. Irrigation use will be determined based on forecasted rainfall. If deemed necessary, the irrigation system would be connected to an agricultural stock pond located north of the proposed mitigation bank on the northern side of Lakeville Highway. The irrigation system would be piped from the stock pond, along the Wheat Creek corridor, to the Halo Ranch Property. Irrigation would only be used to supplement plant establishment of Wheat Creek and associated non-wetland riparian habitat. Tidal wetlands, seasonal wet meadow and seasonal wetland depressions would not be irrigated.

Invasive Species Treatment

No preconstruction treatment of invasive plants is anticipated. Restoration of tidal flows is anticipated to eradicate most of the non-native species, including ruderal grasses that currently exist on the Project Area. The area subject to disturbance from construction will be surveyed during the growing season prior to construction and any necessary invasive plant treatments will be assessed. Treatment protocol(s) will be developed to address any pre-construction control of invasive plants. Treatment protocol(s) may include herbicide application prior to transplant of direct transplant material from within the stock pond.

Invasive Species treatment and herbicide application locations, chemicals, and application rates were not specifically described in the biological assessment or the BEI and are therefore not analyzed in this consultation. Since treatment has not been described or analyzed for effects to listed species, implementation may require reinitiation of this consultation.

Fencing, Gates, and Signage

Lower elevation of southern berm												
Flap Gate 1 removal, connect to tidal flows												
Flap Gate 2 removal, connect to tidal flows												
Excavate southern extent of Wheat Creek & connect to tidal flows												
Install irrigation system (if deemed necessary)												
Seeding, planting, and willow cutting installation												
Demobilization												
<p><i>* Work conducted during the nesting season (February to August) can occur if a pre-construction nesting bird survey confirms absence of bird species protected under the Migratory Bird Treaty Act.</i></p> <p><i>**Due to potential unforeseen delays in the construction schedule, construction activities may extend into November/December. However, construction activities within areas with sensitive resources, such as in-water work, would only be conducted with prior agency approval(s).</i></p>												

Construction Equipment

The following construction equipment will be used to carry out the proposed project:

- 4 – Kenworth 10-wheel dump trucks
- 1 – Bobtail Tractor
- 1 – Excavator – CAT 330
- 1 – Excavator – JD200
- 1 – Motor Grader – CAT 772
- 1 – Dozer – CAT D5
- 1 – Dozer – CAT D6
- 1 – Scraper – CAT613
- 1 – Loader – CAT 963
- 1 – Box Scraper – Case 570
- 1 – Compactor – CAT 563
- 1 – Roller – CAT 433

Haul Roads, Stockpiles and Staging Areas

Temporary haul roads will be used in the Project Area and revegetated post-construction. Excess material that would require haul trips offsite will not be created as a part of the proposed project. Material within temporary stockpile areas will be redistributed within the Project Area and will

be reseeded according to which habitat they will have temporarily impacted. Temporary construction equipment staging areas will be located within upland areas.

Management Actions

The following post-construction actions will be implemented within the Halo Ranch Mitigation Bank to ensure plant establishment is successful and that ecological functions are maintained or improved. These management actions are included in the Halo Ranch Mitigation Bank's BEI. As of the writing of this biological opinion the BEI has not been finalized. Changes to the BEI may trigger reinitiation of this consultation.

Grazing Management Plan

Grazing will occur six months of the year in order to reduce cover of non-native vegetation, improve success of native wetland vegetation, reduce thatch accumulation, and improve wetland hydrology.

Development and Interim Management Plan

The Development and Interim Management Plan includes details of the restoration plan and planting plan for the Halo Ranch Mitigation Bank. Monitoring and maintenance activities entail invasive species monitoring and treatment, minor native vegetation reseeding, and erosion monitoring and control at a minimum. Annual reports will be prepared and submitted to the Halo Ranch Mitigation Bank's Interagency Review Team until performance standards are met. Details of performance standards are included in the Halo Ranch Mitigation Bank's Development and Interim Management Plan.

Interim management begins when the Halo Ranch Mitigation Bank is established and continues until all of the performance standards have been met (up to 10 years or more if adaptive management measures are needed). Activities implemented during the interim management period would include changing grazing practices based on site conditions, monitoring restored areas for degrading conditions and invasive species, fence maintenance, trash removal, and other tasks as necessary. Wetland monitoring and maintenance entails weed monitoring and treatment, minor native vegetation reseeding, erosion monitoring and control.

Long-term Management Plan

The Halo Ranch Mitigation Bank will be held under a conservation easement in perpetuity. After the interim management period is complete, the Halo Ranch Mitigation Bank will transition into the long-term management period. The purpose is to ensure the Halo Ranch Mitigation Bank is managed, monitored, and maintained in perpetuity. Annual monitoring will qualitatively assess the condition of restored areas. Non-native invasive species will be monitored and controlled using state-accepted methods, including, but not limited to physical removal, chemical treatment, and alteration of the grazing regime.

Adaptive Management

Small scale adaptive management actions will be implemented as soon as is practicable after detection of an impact, threat, or significant and prolonged negative trend. Such actions include:

- changing invasive species treatment technique between hand weeding, mowing, flash grazing, and chemical treatment for minor invasive species infestations;
- minor erosion control;
- minor channel stability improvements;
- minor repairs due to trespass; and
- changes to livestock stocking rates or rotational schedule.

Major adaptive management actions will be discussed with the banking Interagency Review Team (IRT) and Property Owner and approved by the IRT before implementing and may include:

- treatment of significant invasive species infestations;
- major erosion control;
- major channel stability improvements;
- major repairs due to trespass; and
- treatment after major natural event such as a fire, flood, or significant and prolonged drought.

These future activities have not been analyzed for effects to listed species and implementation may trigger reinitiation of this consultation.

Conservation Measures

1. The Construction Foreman/Manager will maintain a readily available copy of all regulatory permits as required by each authorizing agency.
2. Construction activities will follow all relevant Best Management Practices (BMPs) as detailed in the Sonoma County Construction BMPs (County of Sonoma 2020 as cited in the biological assessment).
3. Equipment staging, materials storage, and stockpile areas will be located in upland areas only. Soil stockpiles will be located at least 50 feet from the high tide line of the Petaluma River/marsh complex in predetermined locations. If stockpiles are to remain during the rainy season (November to May), stockpiles will be seeded to prevent erosion and runoff. Seeding will occur at the appropriate time of year to ensure proper germination.
4. A hazardous materials management/fuel spill containment plan for the emergency cleanup of any spills of fuel or other materials will be prepared. This plan will be given to all contractors working on the proposed project and at least one copy will be located on the Project Area at all times during ground disturbing activities.
5. Equipment will be refueled and serviced at designated construction staging areas at least

50 feet from aquatic resources or use a secondary containment method at designated refueling areas.

6. Construction vehicles and equipment will be inspected daily to prevent discharge and contamination of soil or water (from external grease and oil or from leaking hydraulic fluid, fuel, oil, and grease).
7. Prior to ground-disturbing activities, a Worker Environmental Awareness Program (WEAP) training will be conducted by an approved biologist to discuss potential listed species that may inhabit the Project Area. At a minimum, the WEAP training will consist of a brief presentation on relevant listed species biology and protection measures to inform personnel working within the Project Area. Contractors, their employees, and other on-site personnel will undergo sensitive species training prior to involvement with construction activities in the Project Area. The program will include a description of the species and their habitat needs, reports of occurrences in the Project Area, an explanation of the status of each listed species and their protection under the Act, and a list of measures being taken to reduce potential impacts to the species during proposed project implementation.

Fact sheets conveying this information will be prepared for distribution to the Construction Foreman/Manager. Records of sensitive species training will be retained by the approved biologist. The approved biologist will train any new personnel working within the Project Area who were not working on the Project during the initial employee education training. WEAP training materials and sign-in sheets should be maintained during construction activities. The approved biologist will collect sign-in sheets for documentation purposes.

8. Excavation of the outlet of Wheat Creek will be completed using an excavator equipped with an open (digging) bucket and operated from the shore/upland.
9. The potential for wildfires will be reduced by parking vehicles away from vegetation to the extent feasible and by the use of shields, protective mats, and other fire prevention methods when welding, grinding, or conducting other activities that are likely to create a fire hazard. The Project Area will have adequate sources of water, shovels, and fire extinguishers available for immediate use. All vehicles and heavy equipment used in the Project Area will have on-board fire extinguishers. During the dry season, vehicles will never be parked or idled so that the undercarriage is in direct contact with vegetation.
10. All trash will be removed from the worksite at the end of each workday to eliminate any attraction to predators of special-status species.
11. All construction haul roads will be clearly identified and marked in the field and construction equipment will be restricted to these roads at all times.
12. Construction activities within the Project Area will occur during the dry season only except as noted above in Table 1 and in measures below for California clapper rails.

13. A Service-approved biologist(s) will be responsible for overseeing the implementation of avoidance and minimization measures. Approved biologist(s) will be given the authority to stop work that may impact a special-status species. The approved biologist(s) will be the contact for personnel who observe a listed species. If a special-status species is observed at any time during construction, work will not be initiated or will be stopped immediately within 200 feet of the animal until the animal leaves the vicinity of the work area of its own volition. If the animal in question does not leave the work area, work will not be reinitiated in the vicinity of the animal until the appropriate agency is contacted and has decided on how to proceed with work activities. The biological monitor will direct the contractor on how to proceed accordingly. The biological monitor or any other persons within the Project Area will not pursue, capture, handle, or harass any species observed.
14. Ground disturbing activities will avoid impacts to existing trees. Fencing, including signs stating “tree protection area”, will be erected outside of the critical root zone of all trees. Prior to the start of any ground-disturbing activities, fencing and signs will be installed and will remain in place throughout all ground-disturbing activities. Any ground disturbing activities that may occur within the critical root zone of a tree will be approved by the County of Sonoma prior to the start of construction and protective measures updated as deemed necessary.
15. Erosion and sediment control measures (i.e., straw waddles, silt fencing) will be installed and remain in place during construction and immediately following construction to minimize fine sedimentation and siltation from occurring. These control measures will be placed at all locations where sediment input is likely to occur, including around soil stockpiles, along the outboard side of the southern berm adjacent to the Petaluma River/marsh complex, the outboard side of Flap Gate 1 and Flap Gate 2, and at the terminus of Wheat Creek where it intersects with the Petaluma River/marsh complex.
16. Construction activities associated with the removal of Flap Gate 1 and Flap Gate 2, and construction along the tidally-influenced portion of Wheat Creek, will be conducted at low-tide to reduce impacts to California clapper rails, salt marsh harvest mice, central California coast steelhead, and green sturgeon.
17. Upon completion of construction activities, all temporary fencing and/or barriers to flow will be removed and disposed of offsite.
18. Construction activities that occur within the tidal brackish marsh along the southern and western berms that could potentially support nesting California clapper rails, will be conducted between September 1 and January 31 when California clapper rails are not expected to be nesting. If construction activities become necessary within the breeding season for California clapper rails, avoidance measures will be incorporated with further consultation and guidance from the Service.
19. All in-water construction activities occurring within the Petaluma River/marsh complex

(tidally-influenced stream, tidally-influenced ditch, and brackish marsh habitats), will be performed within the environmental work window for salmonids. In-water construction activities will be conducted during low tides when possible.

20. Excavation of the outlet of Wheat Creek will be completed using an excavator equipped with an open (digging) bucket and operated from the shore/upland.
21. Prior to the start of construction activities within impact areas with suitable habitat for the salt marsh harvest mouse (i.e., existing seasonal wetland (farmed), perennial wetland, brackish marsh, and tidally-influenced ditch), herbaceous vegetation will be removed from these areas to eliminate cover for salt marsh harvest mice, thereby discouraging them from occurring in impact areas. Vegetation removal will start at the northern extent of this area and will proceed gradually southwards towards the Petaluma River/marsh complex. Vegetation will not be removed during a flooding event that inundates the Project Area, as these are conditions in which salt marsh harvest mice are most likely to be present.
22. A Service-approved biologist familiar with salt marsh harvest mouse biology will conduct a pre-construction survey prior to vegetation removal and will monitor the vegetation removal process. Vegetation will be removed using hand-held equipment (e.g., weed whackers). This will allow any small mammals, including salt marsh harvest mice to escape the impact areas under the cover of vegetation, and will encourage movement of such small mammals towards available vegetated habitat to the south outside the impact areas. All herbaceous vegetation that could potentially conceal a salt marsh harvest mouse within the impact areas will be removed, including all herbaceous understory vegetation along Wheat Creek. All vegetation that is removed will be hauled offsite the day it is removed or stockpiled in upland areas and will not be left within the impact areas to provide potential cover for small mammal species. If deemed necessary due to delays in the construction schedule, it is possible that vegetation within the impact areas will be removed during the fall prior to construction to reduce potential impacts to nesting birds. In such a case, if sufficient herbaceous cover regrows prior to construction the following year, this herbaceous cover will again be removed by hand prior to initiation of construction activities.
23. A Service-approved biologist will conduct a preconstruction survey for California red-legged frog within 48 hours prior to the start of construction activities within the banks of, and along the berms of, the non-tidal extent of Wheat Creek and along the western ephemeral ditches adjacent to the City of Petaluma Ellis Creek Water Recycling Facility. If a California red-legged frog individual is detected during preconstruction surveys, a Service-approved biologist will relocate the individual to an approved relocation site within the proposed project vicinity, at least 200 feet from the disturbance footprint, and within similar riparian or aquatic habitat. Prior to handling the California red-legged frog, the Service-approved biologist will assure their hands are free of toxins or use latex or nitrile gloves to capture the animals. The animals will be moved in a clean bucket containing leaf litter or a sponge moistened with non-chlorinated water. Information regarding the capture and relocation will be recorded.

24. Prior to the start of construction activities, suitable amphibian exclusion fencing will be installed along the outlet of Wheat Creek into the Project Area at the culvert beneath Lakeville Highway. This will ensure that dispersing California red-legged frogs are excluded from the work area. This fence will be maintained throughout the duration of work and be removed once all activities have concluded. It should be installed prior to the time any site grading or other construction related activities are implemented. Fencing, which will be constructed under the guidance of a Service-approved biologist, will consist of a three-foot tall, tight cloth, smooth plastic, or sheet-metal (or similar material approved by the Service) fence toed into the soil at least three inches deep and supported with stakes placed on the inside of the barrier. The top six inches of the fence will be bent over in a semi-circle facing outwards to ensure that the fence cannot be climbed. An opening for vehicle access will be maintained with sandbags placed at the base to ensure California red-legged frogs are excluded. If a hard surface is present and toed-in fencing is not feasible, sandbags will be used to maintain a seal at the base of the fence. A Service-approved biologist will monitor the installation of the barrier.
25. Suitable amphibian exclusion fencing will also be installed along the western border of the Project Area from Lakeville Highway south to the start of the tidally-influenced ditch.
26. If a rain event (more than one half inch of precipitation in a 24-hour period) occurs during construction, a Service-approved biologist will conduct a follow-up preconstruction survey for California red-legged frog within 48 hours prior to the continuance of construction activities within Wheat Creek and/or within the ephemeral ditches. If any California red-legged frog are found during construction, construction activities will stop, and the Service will be contacted immediately for further guidance.
27. If a California red-legged frog individual is detected during construction, all work in the vicinity will halt until a Service-approved biologist relocates the individual to an approved relocation site within the proposed project vicinity, at least 200 feet from the disturbance footprint, and within similar riparian or aquatic habitat. Prior to handling the California red-legged frog, the Service-approved biologist will assure their hands are free of toxins or use latex or nitrile gloves to capture the animals. The animals will be moved in a clean bucket containing leaf litter or a sponge moistened with non-chlorinated water. Information regarding the capture and relocation will be recorded.
28. No monofilament or plastic netting will be used in erosion control measures which could lead to entrapment of California red-legged frog.
29. A Service-approved biologist will oversee grading activities in order to conduct inspections of the fencing and to ensure that stranded animals are relocated. The biological monitor will, at minimum, inspect the fencing on a weekly basis. The biological monitor will be responsible for ensuring that the California red-legged frog fencing is not compromised and will notify both the onsite contractor and supervisor when fencing needs to be repaired.

Action Area

The Action Area is defined in 50 CFR § 402.02, as “all areas to be affected directly or indirectly by the Federal action and not merely the immediate area involved in the action.” The Action Area for this consultation encompasses all areas that may be directly or indirectly affected as a result of activities for the proposed project and the broader area that, while outside the proposed project footprint, may be directly or indirectly affected by vibrations, noise, dust, light, or changes in habitat associated with the proposed project. The Action Area consists of the Project Area (the areas where initial construction activities will occur), a portion of the adjacent property that includes management activities to support the mitigation bank, and surrounding landscapes including a 700-foot buffer from construction activities for a total of approximately 394.12 acres (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Action Area and Project Area from the February 28, 2023 Biological Assessment Addendum.

Analytical Framework for the Jeopardy Determination

Section 7(a)(2) of the Act requires that Federal agencies ensure that any action they authorize, fund, or carry out is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species. “Jeopardize the continued existence of” means to engage in an action that reasonably will be expected, directly or indirectly, to reduce appreciably the likelihood of both the survival and recovery of a listed species in the wild by reducing the reproduction, numbers, or distribution of that species (50 CFR § 402.02).

The jeopardy analysis in this biological opinion considers the effects of the proposed Federal action, and any cumulative effects, on the rangewide survival and recovery of the listed species. It relies on four components: (1) the *Status of the Species*, which describes the current rangewide condition of the species, the factors responsible for that condition, and its survival and recovery needs; (2) the *Environmental Baseline*, which analyzes the current condition of the species in the Action Area without the consequences to the listed species caused by the proposed action, the factors responsible for that condition, and the relationship of the Action Area to the survival and recovery of the species; (3) the *Effects of the Action*, which includes all effects that are caused by the proposed Federal action; and (4) the *Cumulative Effects*, which evaluates the effects of future, non-Federal activities in the Action Area on the species. The *Effects of the Action* and *Cumulative Effects* are added to the *Environmental Baseline* and in light of the *Status of the Species*, the Service formulates its opinion as to whether the proposed action is likely to jeopardize the continued existence of listed species.

Status of Species

California Clapper Rail

Information about the California clapper rail biology and ecology is available in the Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/TMRP/20130923_TMRP_Books_Signed_FINAL.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species’ range-wide status, please refer to the California clapper rail 5-year Review, available at https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/five_year_review/doc6592.pdf (Service 2020). No change in the species’ listing status was recommended in this 5-year review. Threats evaluated during that review and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species with loss of habitat being the most significant effect.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

There are two subspecies of the salt marsh harvest mouse: the northern subspecies (*R. r. halicoetes*) and the southern subspecies (*R. r. raviventris*) both of which are listed as endangered. Information about the salt marsh harvest mouse biology and ecology is available in the *Recovery Plan for Tidal Marsh Ecosystems of Northern and Central California*, available at: www.fws.gov/sfbaydelta/documents/tidal_marsh_recovery_plan_v1.pdf (Service 2013). Critical habitat has not been designated for this species. Threats evaluated during the drafting of the

recovery plan and discussed in the final document have continued to act on the species since its publication, with loss of habitat being the most significant effect. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the species' range-wide status, please refer to the salt marsh harvest mouse 5-year review at https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/tess/species_nonpublish/3630.pdf (Service 2021). No change in the species' listing status was recommended in this 5-year review.

California Red-Legged Frog

Information about the California red-legged frog biology and ecology is available in the *Recovery Plan for the California Red-legged Frog (Rana aurora draytonii)*, available at: https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/recovery_plan/020528.pdf (Service 2002). Critical habitat has been designated for this species, but does not occur in the Action Area. For the most recent comprehensive assessment of the range-wide status for the California red-legged frog, please refer to the *California Red-Legged Frog 5-Year Review* (Service 2022; https://ecos.fws.gov/docs/tess/species_nonpublish/4021.pdf). No change in the listing status for the species were recommended in the 5-year review.

Environmental Baseline

Environmental Baseline refers to the condition of the listed species or its designated critical habitat in the Action Area, without the consequences to the listed species or designated critical habitat caused by the proposed action. The *Environmental Baseline* includes the past and present impacts of all Federal, State, or private actions and other human activities in the Action Area, the anticipated impacts of all proposed Federal Projects in the Action Area that have already undergone formal or early section 7 consultation, and the impact of State or private actions which are contemporaneous with the consultation in process. The consequences to listed species or designated critical habitat from ongoing agency activities or existing agency facilities that are not within the agency's discretion to modify are part of the *Environmental Baseline*.

The Project Area is located directly adjacent to the southeastern most boundary of the City of Petaluma, in unincorporated Sonoma County approximately 3.8 miles east-southeast of downtown Petaluma. It falls within a matrix of agricultural lands and wetlands that border the Petaluma River from San Pablo Bay north to the city of Petaluma. The Action Area is bisected by Lakeville Highway and agricultural lands to the north, south, and east, the Petaluma Marsh and Petaluma River to the south, and the City of Petaluma Ellis Creek Water Recycling Facility to the west.

The proposed mitigation bank area is currently used exclusively for agriculture. It contains minimal infrastructure except for informal ranch roads, a perimeter berm, and a fence and locked gate along Lakeville Highway. A two-room wooden structure built in the early 1950's and referred to as the "Gun Club" on Assessor Parcel Number maps, has mostly been removed with some portions of the wood framing remaining. Access to the property is from Lakeville Highway and is by permission only.

The Project Area (south of Lakeville Highway) historically supported tidal marsh in the southwestern half of the site and seasonal wet meadows in the northeastern half of the site. Wheat Creek, which borders the eastern side of the Project Area (south of Lakeville Highway),

was realigned prior to 1970 from its original location to allow for passage of the creek through a culvert under Lakeville Highway and to improve drainage on-site. Based on historic photos (NETROnline 2020 as cited in the biological assessment) and site history provided by the Applicant to RES, Wheat Creek originally flowed in a southwesterly direction, where it fanned out into what was historically tidal marsh. Wheat Creek also exhibited more sinuosity than its current alignment.

A railroad spur, known as the Donahue line, was built within the Project Area (south of Lakeville Highway) in 1870, when Wheat Creek was further channelized to prevent flooding of the railway. Use of the line was discontinued in 1898. According to the landowner and a review of historic photos (NETROnline 2020 as cited in the biological assessment), in approximately 1950, a berm was constructed along the entire southern and western boundary of the Project Area to restrict tidal activity and allow for agricultural production. Two ephemeral ditches were constructed along the southern boundary of the Project Area that lies south of Lakeville Highway to capture water from other drainages that flow through culverts under Lakeville Highway and onto the Project Area that lies south of Lakeville Highway. With the construction of the berm and associated increase in arable land, Wheat Creek was also further channelized to direct water off-site into the Petaluma River/marsh complex.

On the southern side of the southern berm lies the Petaluma River/marsh complex. This area is comprised of open waters, tidal channels/sloughs, and brackish marsh habitat. The historic Petaluma River main channel runs immediately adjacent to the Project Area in an east-west direction and a small channel connects Wheat Creek to the historic Petaluma River channel. According to historic aerial imagery dating back to 1952 (NETROnline 2020 as cited in the biological assessment), this area has remained undeveloped.

To the north of Lakeville Highway, the Action Area lies within the continuation of the northern extent of Wheat Creek which passes through a culvert under Lakeville Highway, that provides a geographic barrier to the southern extent of the Project Area. The agricultural stock pond located at this northern extent of the Action Area, is an impounded feature within Wheat Creek. The Applicant resides on the property north of Lakeville Highway to the west of the agricultural stock pond.

Wetlands

The biological assessment provided a detailed description of the wetlands in the Project Area but not the larger Action Area. The Petaluma River/marsh complex occurs within and adjacent to the Action Area to the south and west but was not described in detail.

Brackish Marsh

Brackish marsh occurs within the Project Area as follows:

- BM-1: Located along the berm on the western border of the Project Area. This brackish marsh is contiguous with the greater Petaluma River/marsh complex and directly connected to the Petaluma River.

- BM-2: Located within the tidally-influenced portion of Wheat Creek.
- BM-3: Located at the outlet of Wheat Creek which is contiguous with the greater Petaluma River/marsh complex. This area connects to the historic Petaluma River channel through a tidally-influenced stream channel approximately six feet in width. BM-3 includes the entire stretch of brackish marsh surveyed on the southern side of the southern berm as follows:
 - At the outlet of Flap Gate 2 which is contiguous with the greater Petaluma River/marsh complex. This area connects to the historic Petaluma River channel through an open water channel approximately 20 feet in width.
 - Along a small portion of the slopes of the southern berm adjacent to the Petaluma River/marsh complex. The slopes contain elements of brackish marsh vegetation such as pickleweed (*Salicornia pacifica*), located above the high tide line of the adjacent marsh plain.

Perennial Wetlands

Perennial wetlands (PW-1, PW-2, PW-3) are present within the Project Area. PW-1 is located on the inboard side of Flap Gate 1, PW-2 is located adjacent to a soils stockpile, and PW-3 is located on the inboard side of Flap Gate 2.

Seasonal Wetlands (farmed)

Seasonal wetlands (farmed) (SW-1, SW-2) are present within the Project Area. Seasonal wetlands occur in the southern and western portions of the Project Area adjacent to the non-certified agricultural berm, in areas that were historically contiguous with the brackish marsh on the outboard side of the berm. These features are typically situated in slightly concave areas (depressions) in low gradient or nearly flat topography.

Non-Wetland Waters

Ephemeral Ditch

Three constructed ephemeral ditches occur within the Project Area. The ephemeral ditches are located in the northwestern corner of the site, along Lakeville Highway (ED-1) and along the western edge of the Project Area (ED-1, ED-2, ED-3).

Wheat Creek (Non-perennial Stream)

Non-perennial stream (Wheat Creek, IS-1) is present within the Project Area. Wheat Creek enters the Project Area via a concrete box culvert underneath Lakeville Highway, and flows in a southwesterly direction through the site, and eventually flowing into the historic Petaluma River/marsh complex off-site. Wheat Creek has been altered from its original flow line and is

now a linear feature constrained by earthen berms on either side. The Wheat Creek channel is deeply incised with concrete and other debris scattered along the length of the channel. This non-tidal reach connects to a tidally influenced reach at the southern extent of Wheat Creek. Water flows during and for an extended period following precipitation events, essentially throughout the wet season during a normal year.

Wheat Creek (Tidally-Influenced Stream)

The portion of Wheat Creek that is tidally-influenced is present within the Project Area (TS-1). The feature is approximately 50 feet wide between tops of banks and approximately 8 to 10 feet wide between ordinary high water marks. As with the non-tidal reach of Wheat Creek, this tidal reach has been altered from its historic flow path and is constrained by berms on either side. Wheat Creek currently drains into the old historic Petaluma River channel which drains to the new channel of the Petaluma River.

Tidally-Influenced Ditch

Constructed tidally-influenced ditch (TD-1) is present within the Project Area. This ditch is an extension of the ephemeral ditch that runs along the western boundary of the Project Area, it also drains into the old historic Petaluma River/marsh complex.

Uplands

Agricultural Lands

Agricultural land is present within the Project Area. The majority of the Project Area is composed of agricultural fields used for pasturing beef cows and or dry-farming grain, oat hay, rye grass or forage crops for silage.

Ruderal Areas

Disturbed/ruderal areas are present within the Project Area consisting of stockpiles, berms, and roads. Stockpiles are located in the southeastern and northern portion of and are composed of a mix of soil, rock, and debris. Agricultural non-certified berms buffering the Petaluma River/marsh complex, ephemeral ditches and Wheat Creek from the agricultural fields is composed of dredge spoils and upland soils.

Within the Action Area, the Service issued a biological opinion on July 26, 2022 to the Corps for the Ellis Creek Water Recycling Facility Outfall Replacement Project (Service File Number: 2022-0020516-S7-001) for effects to the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse.

California Clapper Rail

The Project Area is segmented into two distinct areas separated by the existing man-made berm near its southern end. The area inboard of the southern berm currently contains minimal wetland habitats while the area outboard of the berm currently contains emergent vegetation dense

enough to support California clapper rails. California clapper rails may also forage on mudflats in tidal marsh vegetation in the brackish marsh adjacent to and within the Action Area.

California clapper rails have been documented in the Petaluma River/marsh complex adjacent to the Project Area. Point Blue Conservation Science detected California clapper rails in the salt marsh adjacent to the Project Area in 2021 and 2022 using the Two-Species North American Survey Protocol for the Ellis Creek Water Recycling Outfall Pipeline Replacement Project (Olofson Environmental, Inc. 2022). Surveys using the Service's 2015 protocol for presence/absence were not conducted for this proposed project or the Ellis Creek Water Recycling Outfall Pipeline Replacement Project.

Based on recent detections adjacent to the bank property, it is reasonable to assume the California clapper rail is present within suitable habitat in the Action Area. However, it is unlikely to occur regularly within the ruderal and agricultural areas within the Project Area and Action Area. Higher quality tidal marsh habitat is abundant outside of the berm adjacent to the Petaluma River/marsh complex and along the lowest portions of Wheat Creek, which is where this species has the highest potential to occur (WRA 2018a as cited in the biological assessment).

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

Salt marsh harvest mice have been documented historically in the Petaluma marshes, but surveys have not been conducted within the past 10 years (Service 2021) and were not conducted for this proposed project.

Suitable nesting and foraging habitat are present within Wheat Creek, the tidally-influenced ditch on the western side of the Project Area, along the berm on the southern extent of the Project Area, and within the tidal brackish marsh habitat (WRA 2018a as cited in the biological assessment).

Similar to the California clapper rail discussion above, it is reasonable to assume salt marsh harvest mice occur within suitable habitat in the Action Area but unlikely to occur regularly within the ruderal and agricultural areas within the Project Area. Higher quality tidal marsh habitat is abundant outside of the berm adjacent to the Petaluma River/marsh complex, and it is likely that salt marsh harvest mice nest outside the Project Area, but occasionally cross the berm into the Project Area at night to forage on grain crops seasonally in spring and summer.

California Red-Legged Frog

California red-legged frog is known in the vicinity of the Project Area, and the nearest documented occurrence is 0.6-mile northwest of the site in an unnamed creek west of the Ellis Creek Water Recycling Facility (CDFW 2022 as cited in the biological assessment).

Areas within Wheat Creek provide suitable breeding and dispersal habitat. Suitable upland habitat also occurs within the Action Area but like the rail and mouse, occurrences within the ruderal and agricultural areas is likely low. The stock pond in the Action Area north of the bank property may provide suitable breeding habitat; however, the February 28, 2023, biological

assessment addendum reports it is perpetually inundated and the Applicant has observed an extensive bull frog population in prior years. Species specific surveys were not conducted. Therefore, based on the biology and ecology of the species, the Service has determined that the frog may be present in the Action Area and may use it as breeding and dispersal habitat.

Effects of the Action

Effects of the Action are all consequences to listed species or critical habitat that are caused by the proposed action, including the consequences of other activities that are caused by the proposed action. A consequence is caused by the proposed action if it will not occur but for the proposed action and it is reasonably certain to occur. Effects of the Action may occur later in time and may include consequences occurring outside the immediate area involved in the action.

Habitat

The purpose and expected result of the proposed project is to restore and/or rehabilitate wetland, riparian, and upland habitats and manage the Project Area in perpetuity for conservation purposes per the BEI. The proposed project is expected to result in improved and increased habitat for all three species. Table 2 shows the estimated acreage of existing habitat impacted and future restored acreage per species.

Table 2. Estimated Habitat Impacted and Restored

Species	Impacted Habitat (acres)	Restored Habitat (acres)
Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse	55.55	107.38
California Red-Legged Frog	0.19	3.78
California Clapper Rail	1.15	59.83

Restoration will require construction and result in some temporary and permanent impacts. The following subsections describe, qualitatively, the impacts to Corps jurisdictional waters.

Brackish Marsh

Brackish marsh (BM-1) that surrounds the tidally-influenced ditch (TD-1) along the western portion of the Project Area will be temporarily impacted due to the removal of Flap Gate 1 to restore tidal fluctuation to this portion of the Project Area.

Brackish marsh associated with BM-2 and BM-3 will be impacted as they will be rehabilitated and re-established as tidal wetland by removing debris and excavating fill material to establish appropriate tidal marsh elevations. New tidal channels will also be established at the outlet of Wheat Creek to the Petaluma River/marsh complex in order to restore regular tidal flooding and re-connect wetlands within the Project Area to the Petaluma River/marsh complex.

Perennial Wetlands

PW-1 will be rehabilitated as tidal wetland and seasonal wet meadow. PW-2 will be rehabilitated as seasonal wet meadow. These activities will result in unavoidable temporary impacts to perennial wetlands due to the restoration of habitat to tidal wetland and seasonal wet meadow.

Seasonal Wetlands (farmed)

Seasonal wetlands (farmed) will be rehabilitated and re-established to either tidal wetland or seasonal wet meadow by excavating soils to establish final elevations that provide for an increase in the duration of seasonal saturation and ponding and promote a predominance of native wetland plants. Additionally, the rehabilitation of seasonal wet meadow within the central portion of the Project Area will include the excavation and filling of areas to ensure proper elevations for hydrologic connectivity. These activities will result in unavoidable temporary impacts to seasonal wetlands (farmed) due to the rehabilitation and re-establishment of tidal wetland and seasonal wet meadow.

Ephemeral Ditch

Ephemeral ditch (ED-1) will be impacted as it will be rehabilitated along Lakeville Highway. This will result in temporary impacts due to the placement of fill material to raise the bed of the ditch to reduce incision. Temporary impacts will occur to ED-2 and ED-3 through the restoration of ephemeral ditch to seasonal wetland depressions and seasonal wet meadow.

Non-perennial Stream (Wheat Creek)

Non-perennial stream (Wheat Creek) will be temporarily impacted due to the placement of fill material to raise the bed of the creek to reduce incision and through the grading of overflow points and lowering of the side berms and banks.

Material will also be placed at Overflow Point 1 and Overflow Point 2 in order to slow flows within the bed of the creek thereby reducing incision and erosion. Impacts at Overflow Point 1 and 2 are considered temporary since the rip-rap will be placed beneath the grade of the streambed.

Permanent impact will occur from the placement of material at Overflow Point 3 to encourage flows to spread out onto the seasonal wet meadow.

Tidally-Influenced Ditch

Minimal impacts are anticipated to tidally-influenced ditch (TD-1) from ground-disturbing activities. Straw wattles or other erosion control measures will be installed within the ditch adjacent to Flap Gate 1 during the removal process to reduce siltation and sediment transport during construction. Mechanized construction equipment will be used from dry ground within the Project Area to further reduce encroachment within this feature.

Tidally-Influenced Stream

Tidally-influenced stream (TS-1) will be temporarily impacted through the excavation of material to widen the stream channel and allow proper hydrologic flows onto the Project Area.

Tidally-Influenced Stream (Wheat Creek)

The tidally-influenced stream portion of Wheat Creek (TS-1) will be temporarily impacted through the excavation of material to rehabilitate this portion of the tidally-influenced stream.

Noise

According to Barber *et al.* (2009), noise levels above 3 A-weighted decibels (dBA) above background levels can result in a 50 percent reduced listening area and 30 percent reduced alerting distance in wildlife while noise levels above 10 dBA above background levels can result in 90 percent reduced alerting distance. The Transportation Noise Control Center (1997) found that noise levels over 80 dBA above background levels caused behavior disruption in foraging, breeding, egg incubation, and rearing of young in various bird species. In a study by Rasmussen *et al.* (2009), lab mice exposed to construction noise levels 70-90 dBA above background levels for ≥ 1 hour/day during gestation led to decreased reproductive efficiency (by decreasing live birth rates and increasing the number of stillborn pups).

During the first construction activities (while the southern berm is in place), several pieces of construction equipment will likely be operating at one time. Using the method described in the biological assessment, the maximum decibel level (Lmax) during this phase will be 95 dBA at 50 feet, 77.53 dBA at 250 feet, 70 dBA at 500 feet, and 66.4 dBA at 700 feet. This phase of construction will occur while the southern berm is still in place, which is expected to act as a noise buffer and further reduce the noise levels experienced within habitat.

Construction activities involved in lowering the southern berm will include ground-disturbing activities that occur immediately adjacent to and/or within suitable marsh habitat. These activities will be limited to the use of one excavator for approximately one to three days in total. The average noise level of an excavator is about 87 dBA from 50 feet away (Washington State Department of Transportation 2020). Using the 6 dBA attenuation rate for each doubling of distance, noise levels will attenuate to 63 dBA at 600 feet from the point source. Construction activities to remove the southern berm will only be for a short duration of one to three days and will occur outside the breeding season for the California clapper rail.

Effects to Individuals

California Clapper Rails

Equipment noise, vibration, and increased human activity associated with project construction or monitoring may disturb California clapper rails by interfering with normal behaviors. These behaviors include feeding, breeding, sheltering, movement between refugia and foraging grounds, and other essential behaviors. Increased human activity and construction noise and vibrations may cause California clapper rails to flush from cover. As California clapper rails disperse away from the area, they may experience increased predation exposure from active movement, by seeking shelter in vegetation communities with less dense canopy cover, or failing to find available cover at all. As a result, displaced California clapper rails may also be subject to increased competition for resources in more densely occupied habitat. The California clapper rail

could experience reduced ability to vocalize with conspecifics, difficulty in maintaining or establishing territories, or experience reduced hours for sleeping and foraging. All of these behaviors can result in increased stress levels.

To minimize these effects, construction activities within the Petaluma River/marsh complex will occur outside of the breeding season to minimize effects to the species. This also applies to all activities within 250 feet of potential California clapper rail breeding habitat and within 250 feet of the inboard and/or outboard side of the southern and southern berms during the breeding season. If construction cannot occur outside of the breeding season, the Applicant has proposed to incorporate yet-to-be determined avoidance measures with further consultation and guidance from the Service which may trigger reinitiation of this consultation.

Impacts to suitable California clapper rail habitat will occur over one season and less than three days in the most sensitive part of the marsh during construction. No permanent loss of habitat is expected. As noted in Table 2, the anticipated result is the restoration of 59.83 of tidal wetland habitat suitable for California clapper rails.

Salt Marsh Harvest Mouse

Similarly, adverse effects to salt marsh harvest mouse could occur from the use of heavy equipment, use of hand tools, noise, vibration, and increased human activity. If salt marsh harvest mice are present during construction, they will likely experience disruption in their normal behavioral patterns. They may respond to construction activities by relocating to refugial habitat within adjacent marsh to avoid noise and human interactions.

Vegetation removal may result in the removal of mouse nests and excavation of occupied habitat may cause mice to flee into adjacent habitat where predation could occur. Construction equipment could run over salt marsh harvest mice that move into the construction footprint. Walking through the emergent vegetation during construction clearance actions and post-construction maintenance and monitoring activities could result in salt marsh harvest mice being stepped on or crushed, resulting in injury or death.

Although vegetation removal will reduce the potential for mortality from entombment or crushing during construction activities, salt marsh harvest mice will still be affected. Individual salt marsh harvest mice that move into adjacent upland habitat may be exposed to increased predation levels during more frequent active movement to forage or seeking shelter in vegetation communities with less dense canopy cover where there are predators present. Displaced salt marsh harvest mice may also be subject to increased competition for resources in a more densely-occupied habitat or habitat which contains sparser patches of suitable food. Disturbance to females from March to November could result in consequences such as nest abandonment or failure of the current litter. Therefore, displaced salt marsh harvest mice will likely suffer from increased predation, competition, and potentially reduced reproductive success overall.

No permanent loss of salt marsh harvest mouse habitat due to construction activities is anticipated; however, 55.55 acres of suitable habitat will be temporarily impacted during construction activities. As noted in Table 2, the anticipated result of the proposed project is the

restoration of 107.38 suitable habitat for salt marsh harvest mouse.

California Red-Legged Frog

Ground disturbance and construction activities may remove, alter or otherwise disturb vegetation and soils used for cover and aestivation, fill or crush burrows or crevices, and reduce the prey base for the California red-legged frog and individuals may be crushed, buried, or otherwise injured during construction activities. Disturbance caused by construction activities may cause individuals to disperse into areas containing unsuitable habitat, and increase the risk of predation or other sources of mortality.

California red-legged frogs may fall into trenches, pits, or other excavations, and then risk being directly injured, killed, or be unable to escape and die as a result of desiccation, entombment, or starvation. Plastic netting and similar materials that are used for erosion control and other reasons could result in the entanglement and death of California red-legged frog, as well as birds and wildlife, due to exposure, starvation, strangulation, or predation. However, the implementation of the *Conservation Measures* will minimize the potential for these adverse effects to occur.

Preconstruction surveys and the relocation of any found California red-legged frogs may reduce injury or mortality from construction activities. However, death and injury of individual California red-legged frogs could occur at the time of relocation or later in time subsequent to their release. Improper handling, containment, or transport of individuals will be reduced or prevented by having oversight from a Service-approved biologist, limiting the duration of handling, limiting the distance of translocation, siting of appropriate habitat for the translocation, and requiring the proper transport and release of the animals.

Removal of shrubs and grasses may increase exposure of the California red-legged frog to predators due to the temporary loss of cover. Measures to minimize habitat removal and alteration such as restoration of disturbed sites with native plant species will potentially provide refuge, food and shelter for the listed amphibian, while also limiting the establishment of invasive and non-local native plants.

Anticipated activities at the agricultural stock pond include routine maintenance activities and limited removal of plants from the agricultural stock pond fringe which may affect breeding individuals, eggs, and larvae. The agricultural stock pond does not appear to currently provide suitable habitat for California red-legged frog as it is perennially inundated, and bullfrogs that would predate upon California red-legged frogs have been observed.

No permanent loss of California red-legged frog habitat due to construction activities is anticipated; however, as noted in Table 2, 0.19 acre of suitable habitat will be temporarily impacted during construction activities. Approximately 3.78 acres of suitable habitat (non-tidally influenced section of Wheat Creek and ephemeral ditches) for California red-legged frog is expected to be rehabilitated as a result of the proposed project.

Management

Long-term and adaptive management include unforeseen future activities that were not fully described or for effects to listed species. Implementation of future management actions generally described above in the *Description of the Proposed Action* may trigger reinitiation of this consultation.

Cumulative Effects

Cumulative Effects include the effects of future State, Tribal, local or private actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area considered in this biological opinion. Future Federal actions unrelated to the proposed project are not considered in this section, because they require separate consultation pursuant to section 7 of the Act. During this consultation, the Service did not identify any future non-Federal actions that are reasonably certain to occur in the Action Area of the proposed project.

Conclusion

After reviewing the current *Status of the Species* for the California clapper rail, salt marsh harvest mouse, and California red-legged frog, the *Environmental Baseline* for the Action Area, the *Effects of the Action*, and the *Cumulative Effects*, it is the Service's biological opinion that the proposed project is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the California clapper rail, salt marsh harvest mouse, and California red-legged frog. The Service reached this conclusion because the project-related effects to the species, when added to the *Environmental Baseline* and analyzed in consideration of all potential *Cumulative Effects*, will not rise to the level of appreciably reducing the likelihood of survival or recovery of the species based on the following: (1) the intent and expected result of the proposed project is the restoration of wetlands and habitat which will benefit all three species; (2) construction impacts will be temporary and limited to one construction season; and (3) implementation of the proposed *Conservation Measures* will minimize adverse effects.

INCIDENTAL TAKE STATEMENT

Section 9 of the Act and Federal regulation pursuant to section 4(d) of the Act prohibit the take of endangered and threatened species, respectively, without special exemption. Take is defined as to harass, harm, pursue, hunt, shoot, wound, kill, trap, capture or collect, or to attempt to engage in any such conduct. Harm in the definition of "take" in the Act means an act which actually kills or injures wildlife. Such [an] act may include significant habitat modification or degradation where it actually kills or injures wildlife by significantly impairing essential behavioral patterns, including breeding, feeding, or sheltering (50 CFR 17.3) Under the terms of section 7(b)(4) and section 7(o)(2), taking that is incidental to and not the purpose of the agency action is not considered to be prohibited taking under the Act provided that such taking is in compliance with the proposed protective measures and the terms and conditions of an incidental take statement and occurs as a result of the action as proposed.

The measures described below are non-discretionary, and must be undertaken by the Corps so that they become binding conditions of any grant or permit issued to the Applicant, as

appropriate, for the exemption in section 7(o)(2) to apply. The Corps has a continuing duty to regulate the activity covered by this incidental take statement. If the Corps (1) fails to assume and implement the terms and conditions, or (2) fails to require the (Applicant) to adhere to the terms and conditions of the incidental take statement through enforceable terms that are added to the permit or grant document, the protective coverage of section 7(o)(2) may lapse. In order to monitor the impact of incidental take, the Corps must report the progress of the action and its impact on the species to the Service as specified in the incidental take statement [50 CFR § 402.14(i)(3)].

Amount or Extent of Take

The Service anticipates incidental take of the California clapper rail, salt marsh harvest mouse, and California red-legged frog will be difficult to detect or quantify for the following reasons: their inherently elusive behavior, propensity to move rapidly through dense vegetation, and their cryptic occupancy of vegetation types resulting in low detectability. Therefore, the Service anticipates take incidental to the proposed action in the form of harm, including injury or mortality from construction disturbance and impairing the essential behaviors of all California clapper rails, salt marsh harvest mice, and California red-legged frogs within the approximate 394.12-acre Action Area. Additionally, the Service anticipates the take incidental to the proposed action in the form of harm, pursue, wound, capture or collect of 5 adult California red-legged frogs from translocation. Upon implementation of the following reasonable and prudent measures, incidental take of California clapper rails, salt marsh harvest mice, and California red-legged frogs associated with the proposed project will become exempt from the prohibitions described in section 9 of the Act. No other forms of take are exempted under this opinion.

Effect of the Take

In the accompanying biological opinion, the Service determined that the level of anticipated take is not likely to jeopardize the continued existence of the California clapper rail, salt marsh harvest mouse, or California red-legged frog.

Reasonable and Prudent Measure

All necessary and appropriate measures to avoid or minimize effects on the California clapper rail and salt marsh harvest mouse resulting from implementation of this Project have been incorporated into the proposed project's proposed *Conservation Measures*. Therefore, the Service believes the following reasonable and prudent measure is necessary and appropriate to minimize the incidental take of the California clapper rail, salt marsh harvest mouse, and California red-legged frog:

1. All *Conservation Measures*, as described in the *Description of the Proposed Action* section of this biological opinion, shall be fully implemented and adhered to. Further, this reasonable and prudent measure shall be supplemented by the Term and Condition below.

Terms and Conditions

In order to be exempt from the prohibitions of section 9 of the Act, the Corps shall ensure compliance with the following term and condition, which implements the reasonable and prudent measure described above. This Term and Condition is non-discretionary.

1. Term and Condition 1 implements Reasonable and Prudent Measure 1:
 - a. The Corps shall minimize the potential for harm, killing or other forms of take of the California clapper rail, salt marsh harvest mouse, and California red-legged frog from proposed project-related activities by implementation of the *Conservation Measures* proposed in the *Description of the Proposed Action* in this biological opinion.
 - b. The Corps shall ensure the Applicant provides all final banking documents to the Service.
 - c. The Corps shall review all final banking documents to determine if implementation triggers reinitiation.
 - d. At least 15 days prior to the onset of any construction-related activities, the Corps or the Applicant shall submit to the Service, for approval, the name(s) and credentials of biologist(s) it requests to conduct activities specified for this project. Information included in a request for authorization must include, at a minimum: (1) relevant education; (2) relevant training on species identification, survey techniques, handling individuals of different age classes, and handling of different life stages by a permitted biologist or recognized species expert authorized for such activities by the Service; (3) a summary of field experience conducting requested activities (to include project/research information and actual experience with the species); (4) a summary of biological opinions and/or informal consultations under which they were authorized to work with the listed species and at what level (such as construction monitoring versus handling), this should also include the names and qualifications of persons under which the work was supervised as well as the amount of work experience on the actual project including detail on whether the species was encountered or not; and (5) a list of Federal Recovery Permits [10(a)1(A)] if any, held or under which individuals are authorized to work with the species (to include permit number, authorized activities, and name of permit holder). No project activities shall begin until the Applicant and/or the Corps has received written Service approval for biologists to conduct specified activities.
 - e. Only a biologist(s) specifically approved to handle California red-legged frogs will be allowed to capture, handle, and relocate them.
 - f. If mice nests are found within the construction area, work shall cease, and the Service shall be contacted immediately.
 - g. The Corps shall ensure that the Applicant immediately notifies the Service of any

killed, injured, or entrapped California clapper rails, salt marsh harvest mice, or California red-legged frogs within one (1) working day of the detection. Please contact the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at: San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office, 650 Capitol Mall, Suite 8-300, Sacramento, California 95814 or by telephone at (916) 930-2664.

- h. The Corps and/or the Applicant shall educate and inform personnel involved in the Project as to the *Conservation Measures* and Terms and Condition in this biological opinion.
- i. The Corps shall comply with the reporting requirements of this biological opinion, including a post-construction report outlining how the *Conservation Measures* were implemented for this proposed project.

Reporting Requirements

In order to monitor whether the amount or extent of incidental take anticipated from implementation of the proposed project is approached or exceeded, the Corps shall adhere to the following reporting requirements. Should this anticipated amount or extent of incidental take be exceeded, the Corps must reinitiate formal consultation as per 50 CFR § 402.16.

1. The Service must be notified within 24 hours of the finding of any injured or dead listed species or any unanticipated damage to its habitat associated with the proposed Project. Injured listed species shall be cared by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person, such as the Service-approved biologist for the proposed project. Notification will be made to the contact above in Term and Condition 1e, and must include the date, time, and precise location of the individual/incident clearly indicated on a U.S. Geological Survey 7.5 minute quadrangle or other maps at a finer scale, as requested by the Service, and any other pertinent information. When an injured or dead individual of the listed species is found, the Corps shall follow the steps outlined in the *Salvage and Disposition of Individuals* section below.
2. Sightings of any listed or sensitive animal species shall be reported to the Service and the California Natural Diversity Data Base ([https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/California Natural Diversity Database/Submitting-Data](https://www.wildlife.ca.gov/Data/California/Natural%20Diversity%20Database/Submitting-Data)).
3. The Applicant shall submit a post-construction compliance report prepared by the on-site biologist to the San Francisco Bay-Delta Fish and Wildlife Office within 60 calendar days of the date of the completion of construction activities. This report shall detail (i) dates that construction occurred; (ii) pertinent information concerning the success of the Project in meeting the avoidance and minimization measures; (iii) an explanation of failure to meet such measures, if any; (iv) known project effects on the California clapper rail, salt marsh harvest mouse, and California red-legged frog, if any; (v) occurrences of incidental take of these listed species, if any; (vi) documentation of employee environmental education; and (vii) other pertinent information.

Salvage and Disposition of Individuals

Injured listed species must be cared for by a licensed veterinarian or other qualified person(s), such as the Service-approved biologist. Dead individuals must be sealed in a resealable plastic bag containing a paper with the date and time when the animal was found, the location where it was found, and the name of the person who found it, and the bag containing the specimen frozen in a freezer located in a secure site, until instructions are received from the Service regarding the disposition of the dead specimen. The Service contact person is the Assistant Field Supervisor of the Endangered Species Division at (916) 930-2664.

CONSERVATION RECOMMENDATIONS

Section 7(a)(1) of the Act directs Federal agencies to utilize their authorities to further the purposes of the Act by carrying out conservation programs for the benefit of endangered and threatened species. Conservation recommendations are discretionary agency activities to minimize or avoid adverse effects of a proposed action on listed species or critical habitat, to help implement recovery plans, or to develop information. The Service recommends the following actions:

1. Encourage or require applicants to minimize and/or avoid impacts to established high quality marsh habitat.
2. Encourage or require the use of appropriate California native species in restoration efforts.
3. Facilitate additional educational programs geared toward the importance and conservation of tidal marsh and seasonal wetlands.
4. Assist the Service with implementing other recovery actions identified within the most current recovery plans for the California clapper rail, salt marsh harvest mouse, California red-legged frog.

In order for the Service to be kept informed of actions minimizing or avoiding adverse effects or benefiting listed species or their habitats, the Service requests notification of the implementation of any conservation recommendations.

REINITIATION – CLOSING STATEMENT

This concludes formal consultation on the Halo Ranch Mitigation Bank Project. As provided in 50 CFR § 402.16,

(a) Reinitiation of consultation is required and shall be requested by the Federal agency or by the Service, where discretionary Federal involvement or control over the action has been retained or is authorized by law and:

- (1) If the amount or extent of taking specified in the incidental take statement is exceeded;
- (2) If new information reveals effects of the action that may affect listed species or critical habitat in a manner or to an extent not previously considered;
- (3) If the identified action is subsequently modified in a manner that causes an effect to the listed species or critical habitat that was not considered in the biological opinion or written concurrence; or
- (4) If a new species is listed or critical habitat designated that may be affected by the identified action.

(b) An agency shall not be required to reinitiate consultation after the approval of a land management plan prepared pursuant to 43 U.S.C. 1712 or 16 U.S.C. 1604 upon listing of a new species or designation of new critical habitat if the land management plan has been adopted by the agency as of the date of listing or designation, provided that any authorized actions that may affect the newly listed species or designated critical habitat will be addressed through a separate action-specific consultation. This exception to reinitiation of consultation shall not apply to those land management plans prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604 if:

- (1) Fifteen years have passed since the date the agency adopted the land management plan prepared pursuant to 16 U.S.C. 1604; and
- (2) Five years have passed since the enactment of Public Law 115-141 [March 23, 2018] or the date of the listing of a species or the designation of critical habitat, whichever is later.

Please address any questions or concerns regarding this response Kim Squires, Section 7 Division Manager via email at Kim_Squires@fws.gov. Please refer to the Service File Number: 2022-0005810-S7-001 in any future correspondence regarding this consultation.

Sincerely,

Donald Ratcliff
Field Supervisor

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